

Pre-Amplifier Kit Manual

Introduction

Fig. 1: SCL Pre-amplifier (protection case and printed circuit board inside)

SCL's pre-amplifier (Fig. 1) is used to amplify an output signal of SCL's self-sensing cantilevers to a higher and therefore more noise resistant voltage level for a data readout device (Lock-in amplifier, atomic force microscope controller, etc.). The pre-amplifier PCB (printed circuit board) supplies the on-chip sensor Wheatstone bridge with a low noise reference operating voltage and reads out the cantilever sensor signal (Fig. 2). The standard reference operating voltage amounts to 2.048 V but can be switched via a jumper to an external bridge supply. The total gain of $G=100$ is provided by 1.) an instrumentation amplifier ($G=20$) and 2.) a low noise as well as a high bandwidth operational amplifier ($G=5$). An offset voltage in the output signal can be corrected by adding an external offset signal or an onboard manual potentiometer offset voltage.

Fig. 2: Principle schematic of SCL's pre-amplifier

Fig. 3 gives an overview about general application of the pre-amplifier kit. The kit consists of a counter-part PCB incl. flat-flex-cable, the preamplifier and an output cable which is connected to a power supply and a data readout device.

If the cantilever shall be operated in the non contact mode (dynamic), you can mount a piezo electric element below the counter-part PCB (CP-PCB). For the mounting you can use an epoxy glue .The piezo can be ordered directly from us. Fig. 3 shows the mechanical setup for the Cantilever-PCB, counter-part PCB and a piezo on a ground plate.

Fig. 3: Pre-amplifier kit (overview)

Fig. 4 shows the parts of the pre-amplifier kit (preamplifier + input/output cables):

- 1) A counter-part PCB (CP-PCB) with a soldered flat-flex-cable (FFC, standard length = 15 cm¹, 8 contacts, pitch: 0.5mm),
- 2) the pre-amplifier PCB inside a plastic protection case and
- 3) an output cable.

Fig. 4: Parts of a pre-amplifier kit: 1) counter-part PCB, 2) pre-amplifier and 3) output cable

¹ A FFC with a length of 5 cm and 20 cm is also available.

Special functions

Fig. 5 gives an overview about the hardware of the pre-amplifier PCB.

Special onboard functions are mentioned in the following:

1. With the onboard offset potentiometer the offset of the output signal can be adjusted to a desired DC level in the range of +/-5 V. No extra external offset voltage power supply channel is needed for the offset correction.
2. If you want to input the input signal via your own wires (bypass the connector), you can use onboard header pins or solder holes. The same for the output.
3. The two heater contacts on the chip are directly connected to the pre-amplifier FFC connector via the CP-PCB and the FFC. From there one contact (Heat_B) is connected to GND via a 0 Ohm resistor. The other heater contact (Heat_A) is directly connected to the pre-amplifier's output connector. Therefore only one signal + GND is necessary to drive the heater. For special applications with only one wired connection to the heater one can remove the 0 Ohm resistor.
4. Change input polarity: At the input FFC connector four pads for resistors are situated. Two resistors are already equipped on these pads. If you want to change the polarity of the cantilever input signal you can change the position of the two resistors to the other two positions.
5. The bridge supply can be applied from the onboard 2.048 V reference voltage supply or an external bridge supply via the output connector.

Attention: In this case the jumper "BS" must be removed before inputting the external bridge supply voltage!

Fig. 5: Pinout of the pre-amplifier PCB and notes for the special onboard functions

The pinout of the output cable incl. the signal meaning is given in Fig. 6. The length of the output cable should be as short as possible to ensure a high quality output signal.

Pinout - Pre-amplifier output cable			
Pin #	Wire color	Identifier	Meaning
1	blue +shield	GND	ground
2	red	+Vs	positive supply voltage
3	green	-Vs	negative power supply
4	pink	Bridge_Supply	external bridge supply; Attention: Before an external bridge supply voltage can be used jumper JP_BS on the pre-amplifier PCB must be disconnected.
5	yellow	Offset	external offset for the output voltage;
6	grey	Heat_A	direct single wire connection to heater; Heat-B (from chip) is connected to ground via a 0 Ohm resistor.
7	white	Output_100x	signal output
8	brown	GND	ground

Connector of the output cable

Open ends of the output cable

Fig. 6: Pinout of the pre-amplifiers output cable

Driving the heater

Our PRSA cantilever types exhibit a integrated heater structure. The typical heater value amounts to 20-45 Ω for a 300x100 μm cantilever (heater shape: meander) and 12 +/-1 Ohm for a 100x48 μm cantilever (shape: rectangle). The heater can be used for thermal actuation of the cantilever (static bending or dynamic oscillation) by applying a statical or dynamic voltage/current to pin Heat_A. The heater signal Heat_A is directly wired from the output connector to the FPC connector on the pre-amp PCB. Therefore, one must be careful when driving the heater. We recommend using a max. effective power of 40 mW (e.g. 1.2 V_{DC} and 35 mA @ 35 Ω) for cantilevers with meander shaped heaters (absolute max. power: 80 mW). For cantilevers with rectangle shaped heaters the abs. max. power = 100 mW. Applying a larger than abs. max. power destroys the heater. Contact Heat_B is directly wired to GND on the pre-amplifier PCB as mentioned in section "special functions" above.

The heater can be driven in AC+DC or AC mode:

1. AC+DC: Sine signal combined with a DC signal half the value of the peak-to-peak sine amplitude. This avoids negative driving signals, which would also heat up the heater and excite the cantilever. E.g.: 1.2 V_{AC,pp} combined with 0.6 V_{DC};
2. AC: For this mode a normal sine signal without DC offset is used. The heater gets excited at the negative and positive half wave. Therefore, only half cantilever resonance frequency ($f_R/2$) is necessary to drive the heater. The readout e.g. with a lock-in amplifier must be done at the second harmonic.

Drawings / mechanical dimensions

Fig. 7: Dimensions of the counter-part, cantilever and pre-amplifier PCB

Specifications

Dimensions (l x w x h)	
pre-amp PCB	48 x 28 x 1.6 mm
Pre-amp PCB incl. connectors	52 x 28 x 7 mm
Enclosure	46 x 36 x 18 mm
Electrical Specifications	
Operation voltage V_s	+/-5... +/-15 V
Gain, voltage amplification	100x
Bandwidth	$f_{3dB} = 2,5 \text{ MHz @ } 2mV_{pp}$ sine input signal
Power consumption	340 mW @ $V_s = +/-10V$ ($I_{Bias} = +/-17 \text{ mA}$) 160 mW @ $V_s = +/-5V$ ($I_{Bias} = +/-16 \text{ mA}$)
Total offset adjustment range	(V_s^-) +1.4 V to (V_s^+) -1.0 V
manual onboard offset range	+/-5V
Output impedance	50 Ohm
Input impedance	3 GΩ 6 pF
Wheatstone bridge supply voltage (external input possible)	2,048 V (voltage reference)
Slewrate output stage	27 V/μs
Connectors and cables	
Input connector (cantilever side)	FFC 8 Pin
Output connector	Header Connector 8 Pin
Input FFC cable	FFC, 8 pol, length=152mm
Output cable	shielded flexible cable, l=1m, open ends

Fig. 8: Specifications of the pre-amplifier